

SKILLS NEEDS ASSESSMENT IN THE TOURISM SECTOR IN ALBANIA - 2024

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Abstract

Skills Needs Assessment (SNA) in Tourism Sector¹ provides valuable insights into the skills' gaps, skills needs and other related dynamics in the Tourism Sector aiming to serve to education, training, labor market and employment institutions and policies. It provides information on: (a) the profile of the sector; (b) the quality and dynamics of workforce and skills; (c) concerns of the private sector related to recruitment and employment, training and technology, and (d) the followed approaches to deal with the existing concerns. The SNA findings clearly show that the sector has grown, the sector is optimistic about the future growth, while the current profile of the sector as well as the LM concerns and bottlenecks might condition the future growth speed and the quality of the touristic offer. These findings, are an opportunity to increase awareness about the sector and offer arguments for further policy discussions among institutions and stakeholders/actors to unlock the identified potentials. Considering the importance of Tourism and Hospitality (T&H) Sector, NAVETQ has established the SSC, to assist the development/revision/ validation process of the vocational standards from the perspective of private sector needs. The SNA findings are an important input for NAVETQ and SSC.

Introduction

The sector and cross sector strategic framework on the economic development in Albania ranks Tourism among the priority sectors. Different research studies²³⁴ has confirmed the importance of Tourism for the country's current and future growth. The importance of the sector is even higher considering its potential to mobilize and promote other sectors' economic development, providing a multiple effect in the national economy.

Albania is experiencing a fast increase of international visitors and has opened itself to the touristic world. As result, the tourism sector is becoming a driver of economic growth and employment, which was confirmed in 2023. An integrated investment approach is followed by the government through mobilizing large public investments in infrastructure and opening the path to private investments including the strategic ones with a particular fiscal and regulatory support.

Certain barriers and obstacles are current and future challenges for the sector's growth such as quality infrastructure and connectivity, insufficient standards, seasonality, geographic coverage, productivity, informality etc. In addition, migration, labor and skills shortages as well as skills mismatch remain important challenges.

SNA in Albania

¹ This research work has been prepared in the framework of a research project commissioned by the European Bank for Reconstruction and Development (EBRD) in support of NAVETQ and SSC. Opinions and interpretation of results expressed here belong to the authors and do not necessarily represent views of the donor and the Agency.

² The World Bank, 2020. Albania Systematic Country Diagnostic World Bank Update 2020.

³ Risi Albania, 2021, Key sectors prioritization in Albanian economy.

⁴ Sectors of current strength are those with the highest value of elasticity in at least one of the two criteria (employment and GVA).

SNA are used as an important tool to collect information on the present needs for skills in the economy, as reported by private enterprises and employers, at national or sectorial basis. They provide a snapshot of skills needs, skills shortages, their dynamics and skills' projections in attempts to better match expectations of demand and supply actors and stakeholders of the labor market. Five SNAs are performed for the Albanian economy as a whole, specifically in 2008, 2010, 2012, 2014 and 2017. In 2021, the first sectorial SNA was conducted for the ICT sector. The SNA for the "Accommodation, food service, and tourism activities" aimed to provide valuable insights into the skills' gaps, skills dynamics and relevant projections in this area, as an input to the established SSC in better aligning profiles and curricula with labor market demands.

SNA 2024 methodology

The general objective of the SNA in "Accommodation, food service, and tourism activities" is the collection of data and information by using a survey with employers. The scope covers all private "active" enterprises in INSTAT Business Register classified under NACE REV 2 Section I: Accommodation and Food Service Activities, divisions 55 and 56 (hotel, accommodation, food, and beverage industries) and NACE 79, part of Section N (travel agencies and tour operators) excluding the businesses without registered employees.

SNA in T&H 2024 targets private enterprises/employers of a sample size of 660 enterprises (out of a population of 8,873 enterprises) based upon three main dimensions: (i) explicit stratification by region and within regions by prefecture; (ii) explicit stratification by type of economic activity; (iii) implicit stratification by size of enterprise measured in terms of number of employees (81% businesses with 1-9 employees, 18% with 10-49 employees and 1% with 50+ employees).

After the fieldwork, the businesses with validated answer were 534 and the final sampling Frame resulted 6,610 businesses involved in Accommodation services (19%), Food and beverage services (71%) and Travel and Tours agencies/operators (10%). The reporting domains are Tirana (43%), Coastal region (35%) and Inland Areas (22%).

Background information

Tourism, sector of priority

Albania remains a strong aspirant of EU accession, which is at the core of the country's development vision outlined in the National Strategy for Development and European Integration (NSDEI)⁵

"[a] dynamic economy, part of EU and WB region, with equal opportunities for all Albanian citizens based on a functional democracy that guarantees the human rights and freedom".

NSDEI is based in three main pillars: (i) Democracy and strengthening of institutions and good governance; (ii) Sustainable economic development, connectivity, and green growth; and (iii) Social cohesion. NSDEI defines four interrelated sectorial priorities, which include agriculture and rural development; tourism; energy and natural resources; and digitalization.

The economic development and prosperity of Albania is tied to the development of tourism, which has a significant multiplier effect on economic activity (due to the linkages with other sectors such as agriculture, construction, infrastructure, culture, transport, manufacturing, food processing, financial services, etc.).

Strategies and legislation

Tourism is the most articulated sector in the public discourse, particularly after the significant increase of visitors in Albania during 2023. The ambition is that along the growth of the sector, infrastructural projects and private investments create the necessary attraction for the development of coastal and mountainous high-end tourism as a contributor to sustainability, to which Albania is fully committed. Recently, the Ministry of Tourism and Environment (MoTE) is engaged to work for sustainable tourism, through an increased focus on the protected areas and the forests, as well as on the service standards. However, despite the favorable geographical position and natural, touristic, historical and cultural resources, the inherited deficiencies regarding standards in accommodation, internal transport, infrastructure, informality,

⁵ NSDEI 2030 is the overarching document outlining Albania's vision for development. All other sectorial policies and strategies needs to be harmonized with NSDEI.

standardization of services, seasonality, technology usage have impacted the sectors development speed and path. In addition, the sector is facing other challenges as results of demographic shifts within the country and abroad, the skills' mismatch in the labor market, etc.

Several sector and cross cutting strategies have guided the development of tourism sector over the last three decades. The first sector strategy dates back to 1993 as the first formal effort to govern the sector. Over the following years, after a series of unsuccessful attempts to formally approve the drafted strategies, the Strategy for the Development of Sustainable Tourism (SDST) 2019-2023 was adopted. SDST aimed at boosting private and public investments, improving touristic services, consolidating and developing touristic products, promoting tourism potential, and supporting the management of tourism destinations. A new Strategy on Tourism is under the preparation process, which aims to guide the sector's development until 2030.

The governance of the sector interrelates with several cross-sectorial documents such as the General National Plan of the Territory 2015-2030; Integrated Inter-sectorial Plan for the Coast 2015 – 2030; Agriculture, Rural Development and Fisheries Strategy 2021 – 2027; Inter-sectorial Strategy for Rural and Agricultural Development (a new National Strategy for Agro-tourism 2024-2030 is currently under the public consultation process);

The Law “On Tourism” and the Law "On Strategic Investments" are the main laws governing the sector. (a) The Law “On Tourism” no.93/2015 introduced certification, licensing, classification of accommodation structures etc. and was twice amended, in 2017⁶ to address issues related to luxury (4 or 5 star) hotels and resorts, informality and consumer protection and in 2018⁷ to address fiscal aspects, simplification of the registration and certification procedures of the accommodation structures. In 2024 a new Law⁸ on Tourism is approved, which addresses institutional responsibilities, including LGUs, definitions of accommodation structures, approval procedures of projects in the field of tourism and the Ministry-Investors agreement for the accommodation structure of 4-5 stars provided with a special status, regulation of the Agritourism structures and activities etc. (b) The law no.55/2015 “On the Strategic Investments” aimed to attract and retain strategic investors.

Completion of the legislative framework in support of tourism resulted in a series of fiscal and administrative incentives, as well as incentives related to the development of specific types of tourism such as the Agro-tourism, through financial support mechanisms and programs of urban and rural development. Under the budget plan 2024 support is given to ensure sustainable development in the Coastal area by extending public services all over the year, development of new products and services in tourism, as well as improving the image of the country by financing important promotional events.

Main developments in the sector

According to the Travel and Tourism Development Index of the WEF for 2021⁹, Albania ranked the 72nd country among 117 countries in the world (Albania is one of the three countries most depended to Travel and Tourism (T&T) in the region, together with Croatia and Montenegro).

During January-July 2023, based on the World Tourism Barometer of the WTO, Albania ranked third in the world and first in Europe, registering the highest increase (+56%) in terms of international tourist arrivals compared to 2019¹⁰.

The share of added value in GDP of the industries directly related to tourism is 3.5% (end year 2022). WTTC recent data¹¹ indicate that the total contribution of tourism sector in the economy reached at a level of 22% of GDP, making the sector one of the main drivers of growth. Currently, the sector has created

⁶ Law no.114/2017

⁷ Law no. 101/2018

⁸ Law no. 30/2024

⁹ https://www3.weforum.org/docs/WEF_Travel_Tourism_Development_2021.pdf

¹⁰ <https://www.e-unwto.org/doi/epdf/10.18111/wtobarometereng.2023.21.1.3?role=tab>

¹¹ https://assets-global.website-files.com/6329bc97af73223b575983ac/645a7321c4f5b39b1d446e7a_Albania2023_.pdf

around 250,500 jobs in the economy (21.5% of total jobs). In the projections for 2033, the tourism sector is expected to generate an additional of 48,500 jobs, thus reaching 27.3% of total jobs.

In 2022¹² value added by tourism industries increased by 40.3%, compared with 2021 (from ALL 52,655 million to ALL 73,853 million). More than half of the added value (almost 60%) is generated by the food and beverages services (I56).

In 2023¹³, the number of international visitors exceeded 10 million, thus registering an increase by 35% compared to 2022 (the increase is mostly noticed during July-August). More than 9.6 million spent more than one night in Albania.

According to a report of 2022¹⁴, it was estimated that more than 70% of all non-resident visitors are of Albanian origins, including, Albanians from the region. Starting from 2022, Albania is seeing a notable increase in visitors from many European countries, especially high-income ones, such as Spain (+57%), Belgium (+23%) and the Netherlands (+36%). These markets are more oriented towards cultural and adventurous tourism.

International visitor spending increased by 18.4%, in 2023 compared to 2019, while domestic visitor spending increased by 4.1% compared to the same year. By the end of 2022, international spending represented 80% of total spending¹⁵.

There is noticed an increased interest of the private companies for the sector. The number of construction permits for hotels and/or similar structures in 2023¹⁶ was 35 (12.9% more compared to 2022), with an approximate invested amount of ALL 5 billion (18% more compared to 2022). Albanian hotels and other accommodation facilities are increasingly present in global booking platforms. While increased access to global booking channels has boosted tourism, it has also created a fertile ground for the informal market (estimated as one third of all accommodation units not registered/licensed)¹⁷.

Priority projects, investments, and local dimension

Priority projects. Referring to the document of the priority policies and projects¹⁸, investments in tourism make up about 7.5% of all investments in the country, while by 2028 this figure is expected to increase to 8.2%. In the list of the priority projects, projects of the tourism are 8 (13.3% of total), with an indicative cost of EUR 517 million (all matured).

Investments. The Strategic Investment Committee has approved a total of 29 strategic projects mobilizing an amount of more than EUR 4 billion; There are 8 hotels classified with 5 stars (6 located in Tirana, one in Vlora and one in Lalez) with international brand names; There are 6 hotels in total (out of which, 4 under construction) with a special status according to the law, with a total value of EUR 155 million; MoTE has certificated 27 subjects in the agro-tourism activity with a capacity of 258 rooms. The total number of agro-tourism structures is much higher, but the certification is not finalized due to problems with land properties; and MoTE has certified 105 Maritime Tourism Operators with a total of 188 equipment.

Local dimension of tourism. More than half of the municipalities (38 out of 61) have a clear touristic profile. With regards to the local Territory Development Strategies, only 7 LGUs do not target tourism in their vision. The majority (53 out of 61) have included tourism in their strategic objectives. There are 50 LGUs that address tourism in priority projects' list.

Regulation and standards

Certification. The certificate is a document issued by the ministry responsible for tourism that serves to prove the fulfillment of requirements and standards for the exercise of the activity.

12 https://www.instat.gov.al/media/12919/tourism-in-figures-2022____.pdf

13 <https://turizmi.gov.al/wp-content/uploads/2023/05/BULETINI-I-TURIZMIT-DHJETOR-2023.pdf>

14 <https://www.undp.org/albania/publications/tourism-and-hospitality-albania-2022>

15 https://assets-global.website-files.com/6329bc97af73223b575983ac/645a7321c4f5b39b1d446e7a_Albania2023_.pdf

16 <https://turizmi.gov.al/wp-content/uploads/2023/05/BULETINI-TE-DHENA-EKONOMIKE-JAN-QER-2022-2.pdf>

17 <https://www.undp.org/albania/publications/tourism-and-hospitality-albania-2022>

18 Decision of the CoM no. 447, date 26.07.2023 "For the approval of the document on priority projects for 2024-2026

With regards to the accommodation structures, standards are linked to the categorization and classification. For the tourist guides, the certificate is issued based on the category and language criteria, it is valid for 2 years and it is used to obtain an official identification number. With regards to the tourist guides, the Ministry encourages, supports and cooperates with accredited institutions for training and information sessions for tourist guides, in order to update and enrich the knowledge of the tourist guide and improve the quality of this service.

Licensing for the Tour operators & Traveling agencies. The Agency and the Tour operator is initially registered with the National Business Register, and after in the National License and Permits Register. The licensed tour operators and travel agencies are registered in the main Tourism Register of the MoTE and currently, information on them is provided at the MoTE website.

The Stars system in accommodation. The legislation¹⁹ regulates the categorization and classification of the accommodation structures. With regards to classification, the hotels and the healing centers can be of 2-3-4-5 stars, whereas the resorts can be of 3-4-5 stars. According to the law, every tourist enterprise, which operates as an accommodation structure, must submit to the MoTE, the request for the classification certificate (valid for 4 years), according to the criteria defined in the by-laws.

The implementation of the categorization process started in 2019-2020 (4 years after the law was adopted), whereas the classification process has not yet started. The new law on tourism investments no. 114/2017 followed by the Order no. 243/2019 are focused on 4 or 5 star brand name accommodation structures, with the right to invest in the casino business.

Based on the self-classification process²⁰ there are: (a) 57 hotels of 5 stars; (b) 465 structures of 4 stars, of which 334 hotels, 98 apartments, 12 camping, 11 hostels and 8 B&B; and (c) 1,223 structures of 3 stars, of which 412 hotels, 564 apartments, 181 guesthouses, 39 B&B, 34 vacation houses, 25 villas, 6 village houses, 5 agro-tourism structures, and 1 camping.

Main SNA results and/or findings

The sector profile

The majority of the surveyed businesses (71% of the Frame) declare “food and beverages services” as their main activity, employing in total 31,750 people (64% of the Frame). There are 3.5 more businesses and more than twice more employees in the “food and beverage services” compared to “accommodation”. “Travel agencies and tour operators” have employed 6% of the employees in the Frame.

Almost half of the overall number of businesses involved in the sector of “tourism, hospitality and food” (47%) are registered in Tirana. Coastal areas have the largest relative share of the businesses involved in “Accommodation” (29%) and the lowest relative share of the businesses in the “Food and beverage” activity (61%). More than half of the businesses in “food and beverage” activity (51%) and those in “travel and tours” services (55%) are registered in Tirana.

The T&H sector in Albania is very young, mostly small and medium size, quite homogeneous in terms of ownership/nationality, and with a strong concentration of activity and employment in Tirana. Thus, the average time businesses operate in the sector is 8 years. Less than one third of the surveyed businesses are older than 10 years in the sector, 44% have five to ten years of experience, while a quarter of businesses are less than 5 years old. The large domination of the sector by new businesses under the fast-growing number of tourists in the country, makes the sector seriously challenged.

“Tourism, hospitality and food” is a largely dominated sector by businesses with Albanian ownership (98.4% fully by Albanian ownership). Very few businesses are fully or partially owned by foreign nationalities (59 businesses or 0.9% of the total), majority of which are involved in “food and beverages” activity.

There are 49,824 employees in “tourism, hospitality and food” sector. The medium and large size businesses consists in 1% of the sector with 15% of the total workforce. The largest employer are the businesses with 1-9 employees (81% of the Frame businesses), engaging 46% of the sector’s workforce.

¹⁹ Law no.93/2015 and CoM no. 730/2016.

²⁰ <https://www.co-plan.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/03/17.-Policy-Document-by-Nevila-Popa-2.pdf>

Medium and large businesses are spread all over the country. In terms of number, the majority is located in Tirana (40 out of 79 companies) and Coastal area (29 out of 79 companies). Both, the distribution companies in terms of employment and number has a similar pattern for the three regions. The employment in Tirana (47%) and in Inland regions (58%) is mostly engaged in the micro size businesses, while in Coastal region it is engaged in Small size businesses (48%).

Youngsters (15-29 years old) make a very significant workforce for the sector, 41% of the total number of employees. Larger the business, bigger the share of young employees. Half of the employees of medium-large companies are young people.

The sector is dominated by male employment (55% males and 45% females). It was declared that employing more males is not because of preference, but because most of the job applicants are from males particularly for “waiter” job position (which is the most populated job position in the sector). 84 % of the Frame businesses have employed owners and family members. “Owners and family members” represent 19% of the total number of employees in the Frame.

The employment of foreign nationalities in the sector is insignificant. They constitute 1% of the total number of the employees in the Frame businesses. At the time of interviews, there were 3% of the total surveyed businesses with a presence of foreign employees (539 people in total). Different reasons can explain the insignificant share of employees immigrating in Albania such as the difficult immigration procedures, cultural and social barriers of businesses’ owners and administrators etc. During the interviews, the businesses declared that at the current moment the main interest of immigrating in Albania is to use it as a transition country to European member countries such as Greece, Italy etc. The presence of owners and family members to the vast majority of businesses and the large domination of the sector by micro size businesses might be hindering factors for the future growth of the sector.

Employers’ concerns

“Frequent mobility of employees” is declared as a main concern by 11% of businesses and as a concern by 65% of them. Businesses seem to be almost the same concerned about “Frequent mobility of employees” and “shortage of supply on the job market” (67%). Practically, both concerns are closely related to each – other. “Shortage in the labor market supply” becomes more pressuring under the “high employee mobility” situation.

“Low salaries” is not listed as a main concern for businesses (quoted only by 6% of businesses), but it remains a concern for 44% of them. The concern about “Labor shortage” has overpassed other concerns such as the “employees’ qualification”, “work culture” and “wage level”.

5% of the businesses declare to not have any concern with employment. “Logistics to accommodate foreign staff” is declared by the businesses to be a minor concern. “Labor shortage” is the most quoted concern, for 42% of businesses as a main one and for 67% just as a concern. “Inadequate qualification” and/or “work culture”, is mentioned as the second main concern by 15% of the businesses, and as a concern for 57% of them.

The major employment concerns in the Frame (sorted)	Main concern		Other concerns		Total concerns	
	number	%	number	%	number	%
Shortage of supply on the job market	2,763	42%	1,656	25%	4,419	67%
Unsuitable qualification level of labor force	1,013	15%	2,760	42%	3,773	57%
People leave the job often	751	11%	3,842	58%	4,290	65%
Attitude of jobseekers / work culture	615	9%	2,868	43%	3,483	53%
Low salaries in the respective market	392	6%	2,484	38%	2,876	44%
Not preferable professions or job description	384	6%	2,416	37%	2,800	42%
Seasonality of job positions	300	5%	1,579	24%	1,880	28%
Logistics to accommodate foreign staff	33	1%	176	3%	210	3%

There are no concerns	359	5%			359	5%
Total	6,610	100%	6,610	100%	6,610	100%

Prospects of businesses

The private sector in T&H is optimistic for the upcoming years, regarding turnover and employment. It results that increased turnover was declared by 42% of the surveyed businesses for the past 12 months and increased employment by another 22%. There are few companies that declare a decrease in turnover (18%), decrease in employment (16%) and decrease of total assets (7%). At least 38% of the business have reported growth in all indicators.

The sector's growth was higher for Coastal and Inland regions' rather than for Tirana. Over the last 12 months, there are 61% of the companies in the Coastal region with increased turnover and 30% with increased number of employees. Tirana was the least grown city over last year in terms of turnover and employment. This marks a very important development feature in the sector that can positively influence the future migration patterns with more people moving from Tirana back to the cities.

It results that the majority of businesses experienced increased demand (50%), while for 38% of them the demand was the same as in the previous period. The businesses are optimistic about the next 12 months. 67% of businesses expect increased demand for their products/services.

12% of the businesses declare to have more than 50% of revenues coming from foreign tourists, while for 19% of the businesses, only 21%-50% revenues are from foreigners. Half of the medium and large size businesses generates more than 51% of their revenues from foreign tourists. 73% of the businesses engaged in "accommodation" services and 50% of businesses with "travel and tours" activity declared to have more than 21% of their revenues from foreign tourists.

Standards and Certifications:

Due to prolonged processes of categorization and classification, the current situation of the sector in terms of standards and certification is very modest. Only a small number of businesses are certified in one or more international standards, with great variance between regions and type of activity. There is a considerable level of lack of information/knowledge and/or lack of need and interest for certification in the sector.

It is noticed that 9% of the businesses in Frame have been certified on one or more international standards for the quality of service. Over three quarters of businesses, particularly the small size ones, have not either knowledge or interest/need to be certified on standards. Different situation is noticed in the medium and large size companies. 59% of the businesses in this group are certified, 2% are in the process of certification while 24% are interested but have not started the process yet. From the geographic viewpoint, businesses in Tirana are better performing compared to those outside Tirana (27% of the total certified/ under certification process/interested to be certified). Businesses interested to be certified are mostly from the Coastal region and less from the rest of the country including Tirana.

Status of certification process on international standards	All companies		Medium and large companies		Region		
	number	%	number	%	Tirana	Coastal	Inland
No knowledge on certification standards	2,951	45%	8	10%	34%	47%	63%
No interest/ need for certification on standards	2,274	34%	4	5%	39%	32%	28%
Interested but not started yet any certification process	751	11%	19	24%	10%	18%	6%
In a process of certification	43	1%	1	2%	1%	0%	1%
Certified already on standards	591	9%	47	59%	16%	3%	3%
Total	6,610	100%	79	100%	100%	100%	100%

Abilities and skills of existing staff

Over half of the businesses in Frame (56%) declare no problems to ensure employees with adequate skills. Businesses located in Tirana declare to have more difficulties for ensuring employees with adequate skills

(54%) compared to those outside Tirana (38% and 33% for businesses in the Coastal and Inland areas respectively). The share of businesses in the Coastal and Inland areas that declare to have employees with the right skills is even higher (62% and 67% respectively).

The results seem surprising for several reasons. There has been high rate of migration of population, particularly youngsters towards Tirana. Both, qualification and employment opportunities are higher in the capital city rather than outside due to their different development stage and investments. The migration and emigration pattern have affected labor market in both areas as well. One reason Tirana declares more difficulties in finding the adequate skills might be related to the higher pressure in Tirana to deliver quality of services and products, which might not be the case for other locations where the tourists expectations are focused on history, culture, adventure and particularly the beauty of sea and nature and less expectations exists for the quality of services. Also, the entrepreneurs outside Tirana might be under higher pressure for labor, which have smoothed their expectations for skills.

Businesses were asked on missing skills for their current employees. “Professional skills” and “ability to work at high load/ intensity in the peak moments” are the main lacking skills (more than 3,000 employees). Only 6% of employees in the Frame businesses demonstrate professional skills shortage. The results clearly show that businesses are under high pressures because of labor shortage staff turnover. As result, thinking primarily for quality of skills sounds unrealistic. The most problematic professions are those of waiters and bartenders, cleaners and helpers, as well as cooks. The pattern of skill shortages is similar for the three regions.

“Frequent change of jobs/ emigration” is the most frequent quoted reason for the skills shortage (45% of cases). The second main declared reason is “insufficient knowledge at the time of recruitment” (36%) and the “lack of motivation” (36%).

“Replacement of staff with new employees from the local market” (66%) and “find a solution within the enterprise” (63%) are the most frequent scenarios businesses use to address skills shortage of the current employees followed by “improvement of used recruitment procedures” (40%). “Outsourcing services to specialized experts/companies” is rarely used (4%) so it is “hiring employees of other nationalities” (2% of the businesses).

Vacancies and Recruitment

There was no quitting employee over the last 12 months for 41% of the businesses. More than half of the Frame (59%) experienced quitting employees over past 12 months with an average turnover rate 39%. Geographically, quitting, is a more spread phenomenon for the businesses located in Tirana (69% - followed by businesses in the Coast, while less mobility is declared by the businesses in Inland areas), while this feature is more spread for “food and beverage service” businesses (61% - followed by accommodation). Less employees’ mobility is declared by “travel and tours” agencies.

Businesses were asked about the number of employees that quit to emigrate. 3,785 employees in the Frame (8% or 29% of the respective occupations that quit the job) left the company for emigration purposes.

The survey has explored also job quitting in terms of occupation. Out of 12,959 employees that quitted over the last 12 months, 6,752 (or 52%) are “waiters”, followed by “bartenders” (11% of the total), both dominant occupations in the Frame’s working force. “Waiters” are those who emigrated the most over last year. It is estimated that 2,060 waiters left the job and emigrated, equal to 54% of the total number of employees quitting to emigrate.

Half of the businesses (46%) had vacancies in last 12 months, but almost all of them have experienced difficulties to fill in the vacancies. Tirana and Coast based businesses have the highest frequencies for vacancies (53% and 50% respectively), while the share of the businesses having vacancies in the rest of locations shrinks to 28%. The vast majority of the businesses (88%) who had vacancies in the last 12 months experienced difficulties to fill them.

The survey results indicate that “Announcements in Job portals and/or Social networks” is the businesses’ most used method to fill the vacancies (selected as a first choice in 36% of cases). “Acquaintances, relatives and friends” is the most considered method to fill vacancies (57%). Filling vacancies through the “public employment offices” or “private head-hunting agencies” is rarely used.

Businesses plan to hire an aggregate number of 8,012 employees on full time basis and 3,611 seasonal staff in order to fill up the vacancies created by those that quit as well as to address the high demand for services/products due to growth.

Analyzing the break-down of 8,012 vacancies for regular employees by region, subsector and size, it can be noticed that the number of vacancies vary from 13%-20% of the existing number of employees, or a country average of 16%. The “travel and tours” subgroup is slightly more active in the recruitment, planning to have 20% more regular employees and 11% more seasonal staff.

The most difficult criterion to be found in job applicants results “work experience” (47% of cases) followed by “correctness/integrity/temperament” (28%). Preferred age appears to be a concern in 24% of cases, while gender is very rarely a concern (only 3% of cases). It is important to emphasize that “tourism, hospitality and food” is constantly in contact with clients and both work experience and correctness/integrity/temperament are crucial to ensure the client satisfaction.

A minor share of businesses (4%) have introduced technologies in the daily operation, while the businesses considering the use of new technologies in the next 5 years are more as an instrument to address workforce shortages and qualification is 16% of businesses in the Frame.

Training

“On the job training from experienced staff of the company” is the most frequent type of training applied by 84% of the businesses, 53% of them consider this kind of training as very important and another 43% as important. Other forms of training such as “Training from the supplier of technology“, “Training from private training Experts/Institutions“, “Training, inside Albania, on Vocational schools/ centers contracted by the company“, “Training from a public training institution“, “Webinars “, and “Training abroad“ are used from an insignificant share of the businesses in the Frame.

Less than one fifth of employees are trained in the last period. Most of them work in large businesses located in Tirana. In total about 7,870 employees or 16% of all employees in the Frame received training. The largest number of employees trained by one company is 335, while micro and small size businesses have trained more people than their current number of employees because of the training delivered to those who left the job.

Tirana has the highest rates of training, both in terms of number of the businesses organizing at least one training section (32%) and the number of trained employees (24% of all the employees of businesses located in Tirana received at least one training section).

Large businesses have better organization and resources to run trainings. 28% of the employees in the medium and large businesses received training in the last 12 months, compared to 12% of the employees in the small size businesses.

It results that the “frequent mobility of labor force” is the main training barrier (47% of the businesses), followed by “lack of training funds” (38% of the businesses). The first mentioned obstacle is almost the same regardless the business’ location (46%-48%), “the lack of training funds“ is a more frequent obstacle in Inland regions (51%) compared to Tirana (32%).

Main findings and Recommendations

Sector profile

The T&H sector’s profile indicates the sector as small, immature, with insignificant presence of foreign investors and foreign workers. Its employment is highly concentrated in Tirana, T&H is a youngsters' and male dominated sector, with a large engagement of owners and their family members in business.

Recommendation: An in-depth analysis is necessary to further understand the influencing factors to the businesses’ size and to the large presence of owners and family members in the T&H sector. Transformation of the T&H sector into an industry requires bigger businesses, increased foreign investments, and an opened and attractive labor market for employees coming from abroad.

Employers’ Concerns

95% of the businesses are facing employment concerns. The main concern for employers is “labor shortage” (main concern for 42% of businesses and a concern for 67% of them). “Frequent mobility of employees” is another concern, which weakens the businesses' position. “Labor shortage” and “Frequent mobility of employees” have imposed a “fear from shortage and mobility scenario” to the T&H employers, harming

their business performance. The large presence of owner's and their family members in the businesses might be a response to address the labor shortage and to avoid the frequent mobility of employees. "Low salaries" are not in the list of the main concerns for most of the employers' perceptions. The salaries for certain key professions in the sector are mostly imposed by the employees and are accepted due to the existing shortage in labor supply.

Recommendation: An in-depth analysis is needed to further understand the reasons and the impact of large presence of owners and their family members as an employment factor in the T&H sector. A proactive and diverse training offer should be conceived in order to increase the labor productivity in the sector. The correlation between salaries and professional qualification and their impact in the business' performance should be further researched (human productivity in T&H sector). A proactive role should be played by the skills and employment institutions in promoting the employability of the unemployed job seekers and working age beneficiaries of social assistance scheme as well as to make Albania attractive for foreign employees and returned emigrants.

Prospects of businesses

The T&H sector is impressively growing. Employers declare increased turnover over the last year and increased employment, which is more the case of the Coastal and Inland areas, rather than Tirana.

The businesses in the sector are optimistic about the upcoming 12 months. The optimism regarding turnover is higher for the businesses operating in the Coastal area. Actually, the revenues coming from the foreign tourists are not a dominant turnover factor. Accommodation structures are most benefiting from the foreign tourists, particularly the medium and large size ones. Many Albanian emigrants are visiting the country, most of them with foreign passports.

Recommendation: The turnover/employment growth bottlenecks in Tirana marks an important development that needs further research attention. The tourists profile and their spending behavior remains important to be further explored.

Standards and Certification

9% of the businesses in Frame are certified in one or more international standards for their quality of service. Over 3/4 of businesses, particularly the small size ones, have neither knowledge nor interest/need to be certified. Most of the medium and large size businesses are either certified, or interested for the process. The businesses operating in Coastal region most interested in certification.

Within the population of businesses engaged in accommodation services, 55% are categorized by employers as "hotels", 8% as "guesthouses" and 31% results "unspecified" meaning that the owners do not know what their business is. "Not knowing" what kind of activity you are involved in makes these businesses vulnerable to guide growth, services' standards and competitiveness in the sector. The most licensed businesses are "travel agencies" (78% either have a license or are in the licensing process).

Recommendation: The institutions in charge of certification, standards and monitoring needs to be proactive on disseminating information in the area of standards and certifications such as legal and regulation background, certification process, requirements and involved institutions, the impact of certification and standards on business development, the advantages of certification and standards, the experiences and best practices of other countries in the area of standards and certifications etc.

There are clear indications from the SNA results that a significant number of businesses are in need to be oriented in their development and growth path. A coaching, counseling and training strategy should be conceived as part of the action plan under the new sector's Strategy targeting businesses in need for information, clarifications and assistance regarding alternative services categories and related investments.

Skills of existing staff

Over half of the businesses in Frame declare to not have problems to ensure employees with adequate skills. Businesses located in Tirana declare to have more problems for ensuring employees with adequate skills compared to businesses outside Tirana. The share of businesses in the Coastal and Inland areas with employees with the right skills is higher, which is paradoxical. Over past years, there has been high rate of

migration of population, particularly youngsters, towards Tirana, a city with higher employment opportunities and better qualification and training offer for both youngsters and adults. The contrary is true for the other locations. Under such circumstances the raised question is: why Tirana entrepreneurs perceive to have more problems with skills of their employees compared to other locations? One possible reason is the pressure to deliver quality of services and products Tirana lives with, while the main touristic offer for visitors outside Tirana is related to the beauty of nature in the Coastal and non-Coastal areas making businesses feel less pressured for the quality of their services/products. It can also be true that the entrepreneurs outside Tirana might be under higher pressure for labor, which have adjusted their expectations for skills.

Higher skills shortage is noticed for waiters, bartenders (Tirana), “assistant chef” for businesses in the coast and “cleaner and helper” for the businesses in the rest of the country. “Cleaner and helper” is ranked the 3rd profession with skills shortage by businesses in Tirana and in the Coastal area. “Waiters”, “Motorcycle couriers” (all in Tirana located businesses), “assistant bartenders” and “pizzaiolos” (a problem mostly in the coast and locations outside Tirana) have the highest rate of incidence for skills shortage (30%).

“Professional skills” and “ability to work at high load/ intensity in the peak moments” are the main lacking skills of more than 3,000 current employees. “Frequent change of jobs/ emigration” is the most frequent declared reason for the skills shortage followed by “insufficient knowledge at the time of recruitment” and “lack of motivation”.

“Replacement of staff with new employees from the local market” and “find a solution within the enterprise” are oftenly used actions to address skills shortage. “Outsourcing services to specialized experts/companies” or “hiring employees of other nationalities” remain almost unused.

Recommendation: Increasing skills of employees in the T&H sector is crucial for the quality of services. There is an increased need for training providers to be proactive and with a flexible and diverse training and skills formation offer for businesses in all territory.

Vacancies, recruitments and difficult to be found skills

Near half of the businesses had vacancies over past 12 months and almost all of them experienced difficulties to find employees. Returned emigrants consists 2% of the employees in the frame mostly engaged as “drivers”, “motorcycle couriers” and “managers and sales agent” (mainly travel sales agent).

“Announcements in Job portals and/or Social networks” is the most used method to fill the vacancies (selected as a first choice in 36% of cases), but “Acquaintances, relatives and friends” is still the most considered method. The recruitment obstacles are higher for the “personnel on supporting job” due to “aspiration to migrate in the future”. Migration results an obstacle of a higher degree, particularly for “specialists of the service”, “supporting personnel” and “sales and Marketing”.

More than half of the businesses experienced quitting of employees, which is a more spread phenomenon for the businesses located in Tirana followed by those in the Coast and less for businesses in other areas. In Tirana the staff turnover rate is near double compared to Inland regions, “Food and beverage services” has higher turnover compared to “Travel and tours”, and “micro” size businesses experience almost double staff turnover compared to the “Medium & Large” ones. The micro size businesses in Tirana are definitely suffering more from the relatively high number of employees quitting the job. 8% of those quitting is to emigrate. “Waiters” are the main emigration contingent in the Frame. “Cleaners and helpers” have the lowest mobility rate.

8,012 employees as regular and an additional 3,611 people as seasonal staff is expected to be hired by the sector in the coming 12 months. “Cleaner and helpers” rank second in numbers after “waiters” (leaving behind “bartenders”). The most difficult criterion to be found in job applicants is rated “work experience” followed by “correctness/integrity/temperament”.

Food preparation, serving, distribution and catering are services with the highest need for skills and capacities. A significantly small share of businesses (4%) have introduced technologies in the daily operation, while only 16% consider the use of new technologies as an instrument to address their workforce problems in the next 5 years.

Recommendation: The future sector's growth is expected to put a lot of pressure on businesses for employment and qualification. The employment and training institutions must identify the measures to address the labor shortages, and reskilling and up-skilling scenarios for the employees. National reforming scenarios should be considered to release the labor force from low productivity occupations through technology and digital solutions.

Training

“On the job training from experienced staff of the company” is the most frequent type of training applied businesses. “Training from the supplier of technology“, “Training from private training Experts/Institutions“, “Training, inside Albania, on Vocational schools/ centers contracted by the company“, “Training from a public training institution“, “Webinars “, and “Training abroad“ are rarely used. The training cost is almost entirely covered by the businesses while other training sources are almost inexistent. “Frequent mobility of labor force” is the main barrier to trainings, followed by “lack of training funds” which is a greater obstacle for the businesses located in Inland areas. 16% of all employees in the Frame received training over the past year.

Recommendation: A proactive role of public training institutions, the engagement of private training providers through outsource services in training provisions, the involvement of universities and VET providers in adult training etc. remains crucial for T&H sector.

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